

Deliverable D5.1

Annotation standards and software, libraries and reference examples

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
D	Deliverable
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
JSON	Javascript Serialised Object Notation
MIFA	Metadata, Incentives, Formats, Accessibility
ML	Machine Learning
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
PU	Public
RI	Research Infrastructure
v	Version

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Executive Summary

AI4Life aims to democratise access to modern AI methods in biological imaging by bridging the gap between life science and computer vision researchers to broaden the reach of cutting-edge techniques. A key part of the widening access is improving accessibility to the rich variety of annotated imaging data that is necessary to train, evaluate, and benchmark AI models.

The work described in this deliverable establishes standards for large-scale sharing of these annotated imaging datasets. These standards were developed with input from community experts in AI, imaging, data management, and software development. We have worked to implement them programmatically, such that they are ready for immediate use, and have created reference examples and documentation to support this use.

1. Introduction

The AI4Life project is part of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, led by the project coordinator Euro-BioImaging and participated by ten partners, four of them being European Research Infrastructures themselves. The project started in September 2022 and will continue until September 2025.

AI4Life aims at bringing state-of-the-art AI-based image analysis to life scientists by establishing and supporting innovative services that target both researchers in the life sciences and computational methods developers in the AI and computer vision fields.

Supporting AI services across life sciences requires coordinated standards for how models, data and annotations are stored and processed. In particular, developing infrastructure and support systems for AI model development and application requires a well-established standard model format. Ensuring that this support is sustainable requires processes for developing, evolving, and maintaining these standards across the community. The aim of WP5 is to develop standardised formats, tools, and processes to ensure that the reference data, annotations, and models that underpin AI are FAIR.

This deliverable focuses on **Objective 5.1**: Develop standards, tools, and processes for FAIR AI reference data and annotations. This objective specifically aims to create standardised ways to represent image annotations. These annotations are a critical part of making image data "AI-ready", so it can be used for model training, benchmarking, and evaluation.

2. Description of work

2.1. FAIR AI workshop

To support FAIR and open access to image annotations, we organised a virtual workshop with expert participants from AI, image analysis, tool development, image generation, and other domains. The virtual workshop ran on the 24th and 25th of January, 2023, with 46 total participants.

Over four sessions, we discussed the following topics:

- What are the important types of annotation to record, and what extra information/metadata should accompany them?
- What are the useful ways (formats, metadata) to share and present annotation data?
- How should we support/allow/encourage the sharing and archival of annotations?
- What are our community recommendations to accelerate AI methods development through sharing AI image annotations? What are the missing pieces?

2.1.1. Workshop outcomes – metadata

The participants unanimously agreed on the importance of having a recommended metadata standard to facilitate the reuse of image and annotation data. One of the most immediate blockers developers encounter when reutilizing datasets is the lack of clear copyright permissions. Therefore, a focus must be put on specifying the type of licence the images and the annotations are under, with a preference towards open licences that encourage reuse, such as CC0 and CC BY.

Another clear priority was access to the annotation's provenance, covering the following questions:

- Who are the authors?
- Were the annotations created by experts or crowdsourced?
- When were the annotations made?
- What software was used to generate the annotations, and what protocols were used for consensus and quality assurance?
- Were the annotations produced manually, predicted by an algorithm, or curated from a prediction?
- From what source image did the annotations originate? The association between images and annotations should be made explicit and not use only the file name.

A related topic of discussion was the possibility of storing an annotation quality confidence level. Suggested metrics for this are self-reported confidence, the variance among several annotators, or the number of years of experience of the annotator.

Regarding biological information, there was widespread support for the use of ontologies and controlled vocabularies to make data findable and interoperable. To facilitate the reuse of data by researchers from different fields that may not share a scientific vocabulary, several participants suggested having a one-line sentence describing the biological application of the dataset, similar to the datasets on the Broad Bioimage Benchmark Collection.

Versioning was also extensively discussed in the workshop. Incremental versions must have accompanying metadata with timestamps and a pointer to the previous version. It is important to preserve the credit to the original annotators.

Another type of metadata that was deemed important is the AI models trained using the dataset, so datasets can reference specific models in the Biolmage Model Zoo and vice versa.

Metadata should also indicate the annotation type (e.g., counts), which images from the dataset were annotated, and what percentage of the data has been annotated from what is available. This latter point is important to distinguish if the absence of annotations means that there is nothing of interest for a specific task or if simply part of the dataset has not been annotated.

Spatial information for non-pixel annotations (e.g., counts of items in a region of interest), including physical measurements or the region that has been annotated, needs to be recorded. Furthermore, any transformations required to link the images to the annotations, such as rotations and translations, should be included as metadata to ensure that the spatial scales match. We also need to account for the possibility of storing multiple types of spatial information for the same instance (e.g., for the same cell: cell segmentation and coordinates of transcription sites).

Finally, general image metadata needs to be stored. The Biolmage Archive has adopted REMBI (Recommended Metadata for Biological Images) as its metadata model, which covers most of the points discussed in the workshop.

2.1.2. Workshop outcomes – formats

Another primary topic of the workshop was to agree on what file formats and dataset structures are the most useful for sharing and reusing annotation data. Several formats used in the community were carefully considered and the following emerged as the preferred options:

Formats for images and pixel/voxel annotations:

The workshop participants overwhelmingly agreed that Next-Generation File Format (NGFF) specifications from the Open Microscopy Environment (OME) are one of the best ways to store and serve AI data. NGFFs such as OME-Zarr are open, which increases interoperability. OME-Zarr is also cloud-ready, scalable, and annotations such as segmentation masks can be packaged with the image data allowing provenance tracking. There are also several OME-Zarr visualisation tools for raw data and annotations and tools for format conversion.

Another useful format for annotation data, used in other fields but relatively new for bioimages, is COCO (Common Objects in Context). COCO has multiple annotation types, like segmentations and classes, that are saved in JSON, and it is language agnostic. However, COCO was developed with computer-vision tasks in mind, thus its performance on multi-dimensional bioimages needs to be examined first.

Formats for tables:

Current developments in the NGFF community are concentrating on developing table annotation support. One of the options being considered are AnnData objects, which store annotated matrices in memory and on disk. Importantly, some participants raised the necessity to export tables to CSV or TSV as portability to statistical tools is required for some applications.

Formats for geometrical annotations:

Another specification widely discussed during the workshop was GeoJSON. This multi-language format supports several geometrical data types which makes it ideal for storing information about polygons and shapes. However, GeoJSON works more efficiently with 2D data, making its application to 3D datasets less clear. An alternative to store 3D shape annotations is EMDB-SFF, an open segmentation format that also supports structured biological annotation.

2.1.3 Further workshop summary

A full document summarising the workshop outcomes is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7681687>, which we summarise with the acronym MIFA (Metadata, Incentives, Formats, Accessibility). A further [detailed description of the outcomes](#) of the workshop was published on the AI4Life website and newsletter to reach a wider audience. Figure 1 gives an overview of these outcomes.

Figure 1 – A visual summary of the workshop recommendations

2.2. Annotation schema specification + code library

To implement the community recommendations, we developed schema (formal implementations of the community guidance on necessary metadata) using the LinkML language. These schema, together with worked examples of metadata adherent to the schema, full documentation and code examples, are publicly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/BiolImage-Archive/bia-mifa-models>, with a version of record archived at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8246386>.

A key component of the annotation standards is the set of specific metadata items that are required to maximise the reuse of value of shared image annotations. **Table 1** provides a summary of these, together with explanations of each component.

The software code provides tools for working with the schema programmatically – for example, data classes and enumerations for the Python programming language (see **Figure 2** for an example). It also includes developer-oriented documentation which provides detailed descriptions of each component of the schema (see **Figure 3** for example documentation for one of the components).

Attribute	Comments
Authors and contact	People involved in creating or curating annotations. Include contact information, such as email, ORCID iD, GitHub account, or Google Scholar link.
Annotation overview	Short description of the annotation and how it was generated.
Annotation type	Annotation type, for example, class labels, segmentation mask, object counts
Annotation method	Crowdsourced or expertly annotated, produced by a human or software (e.g., synthetic data or silver-standard data), software used and protocols used for consensus and quality assurance.
Annotation confidence level	Confidence on annotation accuracy (e.g., self-reported confidence, the variance among several annotators, or the number of years of experience of the annotator).
Annotation criteria	Rules used to generate annotations. For example, when counting cells in an image, at what point a dividing cell is considered two different cells?
Annotation coverage	Which images from the dataset were annotated, and what percentage of the data has been annotated from what is available?
Source image association	Association between annotations and the source images from which they originated. If the annotation refers to a dataset separate from that containing the annotations, it should include the unique identifier for that dataset.
Transformations	Any coordinate transformation required to link the images to the annotations, such as rotations and translations.
Spatial information	Spatial information for non-pixel annotations (e.g., counts of items in a region of interest), including physical measurements or the region that has been annotated. If coordinates for non-rasterized annotations are stored in units other than pixels (e.g. μm), the relevant information must be detailed in this field.
Creation time	Date and time when the annotation was created.

Table 1 – Metadata fields to describe annotations

```
# Enumerations
class AnnotationType(EnumDefinitionImpl):

    class_labels = PermissibleValue(
        text="class_labels",
        description="tags that identify specific features, patterns or classes in images")
    bounding_boxes = PermissibleValue(
        text="bounding_boxes",
        description="rectangles completely enclosing a structure of interest within an image")
    counts = PermissibleValue(
        text="counts",
        description="number of objects, such as cells, found in an image")
    segmentation_mask = PermissibleValue(
        text="segmentation_mask",
        description="an image, the same size as the source image, with the value of each pixel representing some biological identity")

    _defn = EnumDefinition(
        name="AnnotationType",
    )
```

Figure 2 – Example Python language code supporting programmatic use of the metadata schema

 bia-mifa-models
🔍 Search

bia-mifa-models

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About

Slot: annotation_coverage

Which images from the dataset were annotated, and what percentage of the data has been annotated from what is available

URI: [bia_mifa_models:annotation_coverage](#)

Applicable Classes

Name	Description	Modifies Slot
Annotations	A set of annotations for an AI-ready dataset	no

Figure 3 – Example documentation for a component of the annotation metadata

2.3. Reference examples

To demonstrate the utility of images accompanied by well-described annotations, we have compiled a collection of “AI-ready” datasets. These reference examples are available here as part of the BioImage Archive’s collections: <https://bit.ly/ai-ready-bioimage-data>. They span different imaging domains, including bright-field microscopy, fluorescence imaging and ultrasound.

Each example provides both experimentally captured images and associated segmentation masks. These image annotations and their accompanying metadata follow the community-established guidelines described above, and are accessible both via a web portal and programmatically. An example of the presentation is given in Figure 4.

ALPHA

S-BIAD634

An annotated fluorescence image dataset for training nuclear segmentation methods

Released: 2023-03-07

By: Sabine Taschner-Mandl, Inge M. Ambros, Peter F. Ambros, Klaus Beiske, Allan Hanbury, Wolfgang Doerr, Tamara Weiss, Maria Berneder, Magdalena Ambros, Eva Bozsaky, Florian Kromp, Teresa Zulueta-Coarasa

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Study Information

Images

Annotations

Models used

In a nutshell

388 images

388 annotations

Study size: 472.2MiB

Filetype breakdown:

- .jpg: 79 (16.6MiB)
- .png: 115 (1.5MiB)
- .svg: 79 (4.1MiB)
- .tif: 194 (450.0MiB)
- .txt: 1 (3.1KiB)

License : CC0

This dataset has

segmentation masks

test data

training data

ground truth annotations

Example image for this dataset

Example annotation for this dataset

Figure 4 – Example dataset containing both raster images and segmentations masks, together with metadata following the community standards

2.4 Conversion and packaging code

To support the use of the recommended formats, in particular the emerging community standard OME-Zarr, we created software tools designed to enable the conversion of individual images and segmentations into a single OME-Zarr package. Packing images and segmentations together will facilitate provenance tracking and data reuse. This code and usage instructions are available on Github <https://github.com/BiolImage-Archive/bia-images-masks-to-omezarr>, with a version archived at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8248712>.

The code provides a command line interface for both converting images or annotations to OME-Zarr, and combining them into a single container. For example, the invocation:

```
python convert_images_and_masks_to_omezarr.py /path/to/image /path/to/mask
```


will create a new OME-Zarr containing both an image and corresponding segmentation mask.

3. Conclusion

The image data annotation standards that we have developed are community-driven and meet a critical need for the life sciences imaging AI community. Full schemas, reference examples, and supporting software code enable immediate use by scientists and developers. These standards will help both data producers and consumers and accelerate the development of AI tools for bioimage analysis.

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